

Evaluation of Root Fracture Resistance of Methacrylate Resin Based Sealer (Meta SEAL) and Zinc-oxide Eugenol Sealer after Endodontic Treatment

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Abstract: This study examined how zinc oxide eugenol sealers and MetaSEAL affect endodontically treated teeth's ability to withstand fractures. The working length of forty recently extracted human mandibular premolar teeth was measured, the decayed teeth were decoronated up to the cemento-enamel junction, pulp remnants were removed, and the teeth were biomechanically prepared using a Protaper rotary file system up to F3. Following that, the teeth were split into two groups, each containing twenty teeth. Separated once more, this time into subgroups A and B. Subgroup A was obturated using a lateral condensation technique, while Subgroup B was obturated using a matched taper single cone approach. Group 1 used Meta SEAL endodontic sealer for obturation, while Group 2 used zinc oxide eugenol sealer. Ultimately, they were placed vertically within an acrylic resin block, and a universal testing machine (Hounsfield, H1OKS, UK) was used to assess their fracture strength. The force necessary to fracture was measured and examined in Newtons. Significant results were reported as p-values, and students't-test was used for statistical analysis. The results showed that in both approaches, Meta SEAL outperformed Zinc Oxide Eugenol Sealer in terms of fracture resistance force values. Statistical analysis revealed that there was no discernible variation among the experimental groups. In conclusion, the results of this vertical root fracture resistance test suggest that Meta SEAL, a sealer based on methacrylate resin, may be a better material option than zinc oxide eugenol for extending the life of endodontically treated teeth.

Key words: Lateral condensation technique, Single cone technique, Fracture resistance, Meta SEAL, Zinc oxide eugenol

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Accepted: 30 January, 2024; **Published:** 22 February, 2024

How to cite this article: Rahela Yeasmin, AKM Bashar, Humayan Kabir, Sabequn Nahar-E-Farzana, Tania Parveen, Mozammal Hossain (2024) Evaluation of Root Fracture Resistance of Methacrylate Resin Based Sealer (Meta SEAL) and Zinc-oxide Eugenol Sealer after Endodontic Treatment. *North American Academic Research*, 7(1), 120-128. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11002598>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

After endodontic treatment, the root fracture susceptibility increased since there was less sound dental structure left. Caries-damaged tooth structure that is in good condition, access cavity preparation, reaming and filing, and final restoration preparation. Excessive obturation pressure, dentin dryness, and the loss of tooth structure are all consequences of endodontic treatments.¹ Materials used for obturation are thought to be essential for supplying endodontically treated teeth with strength. The substance most frequently used for root canal obturation is gutta-percha combined with sealant.² Because gutta-percha has a low modulus of elasticity and cannot bond with dentin, it is crucial to increase the sealer's bond ability to dentin.^{3,4}

In order to bind to the dentin and the core material, the sealer needs to have sufficient cohesive strength to hold the obturation together. This theory accelerates the creation of sticky root canal sealants.⁵ Adhesion plays a critical role in restorative procedures because of its greater sealing ability, which reduces coronal and apical leakage and prevents filling material displacement. One of the most important requirements for a root canal sealer is to be able to successfully create a monoblock with the core filling material and have a higher fracture resistance.⁴ It was stated that using an adhesive sealer to completely fill the canal space with a solid mass devoid of gaps and composed of various materials and interfaces may result in the creation of a monoblock, which would strengthen the seal and increase its resistance to fracture of the filled canal.⁵⁻⁷

There is a wide range of endodontic sealers that can be purchased commercially, including zinc oxide eugenol-based sealers, glass ionomer-based sealers, MTA-based sealers, Endo-sequence bio-ceramic sealers, and calcium phosphate-based sealers. The most common type of endodontic sealer is zinc oxide eugenol sealer.⁸ Compared to resin-based sealers, zinc oxide-based sealers have lower shrinkage and persist longer as antibacterial agents. They are also easier to handle.⁹ Despite its lengthy and successful history of usage in root canal obturation, post-treatment difficulties arise from leakage and recontamination of the root canal system as a result of eugenol or zinc oxide loss from continual hydrolysis.^{10, 11}

Meta SEAL, a fourth-generation methacrylate resin, is a novel resin-based obturation substance that was released recently. Commercially available in liquid and powder form, Meta SEAL (Parkell Inc., Edgewood, NY, USA) is a fourth generation self-adhesive dual-cure polymethyl methacrylate resin based sealer. Whereas the powder is made up of a combination of zirconia oxide filler, silicon dioxide filler, and a polymerization initiator, the liquid contains an acidic 4-methacryloxyethyl trimellitate anhydride (4-META) resin monomer and photoinitiator.¹² It can diffuse through the demineralized dentin surface to encourage the creation of the hybrid layer following polymerization. It can also bind to the dentin and the core materials at the same time.^{13, 14} Additionally, it reduces application time, does away with the requirement for a separate etching and bonding phase, and lessens the possibility of errors during each bonding stage.¹⁵ Furthermore, it strengthens the endodontically treated teeth's resistance to fracture by concurrently bonding to the dentin and the core components, forming a monoblock.¹⁶ As far as we are aware, no research has examined the impact of zinc oxide eugenol-based sealer and Meta SEAL methacrylate resin-based sealer on the ability of roots filled with them to withstand fracture in combination with gutta-percha, which was utilized in this study.

Materials and Methods

The Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), and the Department of Pilot Plant and Process Development Center, BCSIR, carried out this quasi-experimental study design. October 2020 to September 2021 was the study period. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) of BSMMU provided ethical clearance. Forty recently extracted human mandibular premolar teeth that met the study's inclusion requirements were chosen.

The roots' mesiodistal (4-6 mm) and buccolingual (5-7 mm) diameters were measured. A preoperative radiograph of the extracted teeth was obtained, and any pre-existing cracks craze line, and root fractures were excluded using a dental

surgical loupe. After that, a diamond disk was used to decoronate the teeth up to the cemento-enamel junction, creating a specimen that measured 14 mm. This specimen was then put through biomechanical preparation. With the use of a 10 # K file, the apical foramen patency was assessed after the access cavity was made using a diamond round bur # 4. Using a barbed broach, the residual pulp from the radicular section was extracted. Following that, the file was taken out of the root canal, and the working length was measured one millimeter less than the apical foramen. For each root canal, an apical size of 30 (size F3) was instrumented using the rotating Pro-Taper file system. Apart than these tools, a 27-gauge needle and 5 cc of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite were used for irrigation. The No. 15 K file was used for recapitulation in order to protect the patent foramen Apical. Following instrumentation, 5 milliliters of 17% ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid were irrigated to eliminate the smear layer. To get rid of any last traces of acid, 5 milliliters of sterile water were rinsed. Sterilized paper points were used to dry the entire prepared channel. Next, two groups of teeth were randomly assigned. Group 2 for Zinc oxide eugenol sealer with two subgroups for matched taper single cone approach and lateral condensation technique. Group 1 used MetaSEAL endodontic sealer with both the technique.

Sample size was calculated according to following formula:

$$n = \frac{(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2)(Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-B})^2}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2}$$

Where,

n= sample size, Mean value of $\mu_1=30.93$, Mean value of $\mu_2=27.86$, Standard deviation $\sigma_1=2.17$
Standard deviation $\sigma_2=2.12$, $Z_{1-\alpha/2}=1.96$ (Z value at 5% level of significance).
 $Z_{1-B}=Z_{0.80}=0.842$ (from Z table) at 80% power of the test.

$$n = \frac{(4.7089 + 4.4944)(2.802)^2}{(-3.07)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{\{(2.17)^2 + (2.12)^2\}(1.96 + 0.842)^2}{(27.86 - 30.93)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{9.2033 \times 7.85}{9.4249} = 7.665 \approx 8$$

Group sample size of 8 and 8 achieve 80.704% power to reject the null hypothesis of equal means when the population mean differences is $\mu_2 - \mu_1 = 27.86 - 30.93 = -3.07$ with standard deviations of 2.17 for group 1 (σ_1) and 2.12 for group 2 (σ_2), and with a significance level (alpha) of 0.050. The estimated sample size was found to be total of 8 for each group and 4 for the each subgroup. But the recommended sample size was increased up to 10 for the subgroups of the experimental group and total sample size was 40.

Group 1: Gutta-percha and Meta SEAL endodontic sealer

Subgroup A (lateral condensation technique)

The lateral condensation technique and Meta SEAL endodontic sealer were used to obturate the canals in this group. The Meta SEAL sealer powder and liquid were combined in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. Using a plastic spatula that came in the kit box from the manufacturer, three drops of Meta SEAL liquid and one scoop of powder were combined on the mixing pad to create a uniform texture. This was then put in the root canal using a finger spreader that rotated counterclockwise. After applying the ready sealer to the master gutta-percha cone, it was carefully placed into the canal until it reached the working length. Using a finger spreader, lateral compaction was carried

out. An auxiliary gutta-percha cone was treated with the same sealer and inserted into the canal. The surplus material was removed from the canal orifice after obturation and condensed with a plugger 1 mm below the canal entrance. The access cavity was then temporarily filled and sealed.

Subgroup B (matched taper single-cone technique)

MetaSEAL and the matched taper single-cone approach were used to obturate the canals. Using a finger spreader, the sealer was applied to the canal wall after being blended in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. After being sealed with sealer, an F3 master gutta-percha cone (Dentply, Maillefer) with good tug-back was carefully placed into the canal until the working length was reached.

Group 2: Gutta-percha and Zinc-oxide eugenol sealer

Subgroup A (lateral condensation technique)

In this group, teeth were obturated with gutta-percha using the lateral compaction technique after zinc oxide powder and eugenol were combined to a sealer consistency. Using a spatula, eugenol liquid and zinc oxide powder were combined into a homogeneous, creamy mixture on a sterile glass slab. The sealer was then rotated counterclockwise into the root canal using a finger spreader. The prepared sealer was then applied to the apical portion of the master cone, and it was gradually inserted into the canal to attain the working length. Finger spreaders were used to accomplish lateral compaction, and auxiliary gutta-percha cones were treated with the same sealer before being placed inside the canal. The excess material was sheared off, and the access chamber and canal entrance were sealed with temporary filling material by using a plugger positioned one millimeter below.

Subgroup B: matched taper single-cone technique

The matched taper single-cone method and zinc oxide-eugenol sealer were used to obturate the canals. Once sealed, a good tug-back F3 master gutta-percha cone (Dentply, Maillefer) was gradually introduced into the canal until the working length was attained. A radiograph was then used to confirm the root canal obturation's quality. For seven days, all of the roots were kept at 37°C and 100% relative humidity to guarantee a full set of sealer.

Preparation for fracture resistance test

Using a specially designed stainless steel mold holder, all of the roots were vertically inserted in self-curing acrylic resin blocks following the setting of the sealer and temporary restorative substance. Eight mm of the root length was visible when all of the roots were put in the resin blocks. A universal testing machine was used to perform the fracture resistance test (Hounsfield, H1OKS, UK). Each acrylic resin block was set on the specially designed metallic jaw, which was fastened with a metal screw to the lower plate of the universal testing machine (Hounsfield, H1OKS, UK). The upper plate of the universal testing machine was used to modify a specially designed cylindrical metal rod with a 2 mm diameter and a sharp-ended conical tip. The metal rod's tip was positioned in the middle of the canal opening. Vertical fracture was caused by applying force vertically to the root. Up until the root fracture, each specimen was exposed to a gradually rising vertical force at a rate of 1 mm/min. At 00, the vertical load was applied in the direction of the root's long axis. The point at which the applied force suddenly drops sharply or where a frank fracture of the specimen is seen was designated as the fracture. At this time, the fracture resistance test was stopped, and the force needed to fracture the root was calculated in Newtons.

Results

Subgroup A: Based on an analysis of all 20 samples—10 samples from each group—Meta seal outperformed Zinc Oxide Eugenol Sealer. In comparison to Zn O (311.360 N), the resin sealer Meta seal (363.600 N) demonstrated higher fracture resistance; nevertheless, the difference was not statistically significant ($P < 0.187$).

Name	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Meta Seal	10	363.600	21.08464	0.187
Zn O	10	311.360	118.4284	

figure: 1

Sub group-B: Upon analyzing the outcomes of all 20 experiments, 10 samples from each group demonstrated that Meta seal outperformed Zn O. The resin sealer Meta seal (373.600 N) showed greater fracture resistance than Zn O (311.360 N), however this difference was not statistically significant ($P > 0.119$).

Table 2: Mean and SD in fracture force for Matched taper single cone technique

Name	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Meta Seal	10	373.600	20.0714	0.119
Zn O	10	311.360	118.42844	

figure: 2

Discussion

The mechanical characteristics of the tooth are altered by endodontic therapy; functional and para-functional loads may cause fatigue failure. According to a study using finite element analysis, circular canals have a more uniform and lower distribution of stresses than oval canals, which have higher stresses in the cervical and middle thirds, as well as the labial and lingual canal extensions. The mid-to-apical region of the majority of premolar samples had a circular cross-

section, which may have led to a consistent distribution of load and also simulated the clinical setting when chewing forces are maximal.¹⁷

To replicate clinical scenarios, fracture resistance tests were conducted in various studies utilizing cyclic loading and applying force in various directions.¹⁸ Despite the fact that numerous studies have shown that force is equally transmitted when applied vertically along the tooth's long axis.^{19, 20} Like prior studies, we assess the impact of a root canal sealer on the fracture resistance of teeth filled with roots by applying a single load till breakage.¹⁶

This study used a single-cone obturation technique to exclude the wedging forces of the spreaders during lateral condensation.²¹ As because a number of studies have demonstrated that the single-cone technique outperforms other obturation techniques in strengthening teeth's resistance to breakage.^{22, 23} For the purpose of standardizing the apical canal diameter of the samples, all roots were prepared to an apical size of 30, or ProTaper size F3. The smear layer was removed using a routine irrigation regimen that included EDTA and sodium hypochlorite, as this combination has been proven to improve bonding of the materials evaluated to the dentinal surface of the root.²⁴

It is stated that the primary benefits of the Meta SEAL sealer are an enhanced bond and the creation of a monoblock root canal obturation. According to the manufacturer, MetaSEAL can generate a hybrid-like layer that bonds with gutta-percha. When combined with a matched taper single-cone approach, Meta SEAL has been indicated to comparatively provide void-free and gap-free surfaces, and its adhesion ability is high enough to combat shrinkage strains.²⁵ In our investigation, we discovered that, in the case of Meta SEAL, the single cone approach had a stronger binding than the lateral obturation strategy. According to a study by Ershev et al.¹⁵, this could be caused by thicker sealers that can partially offset the high theoretical configuration factors in the root canals and lower bond strength in the lateral condensation technique because finger spreaders disrupt mature bonds and thin the sealer layers.

The Stiegemeier et al. 2009 study supports the current study's finding that there is no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between the zinc-oxide eugenol sealer group and the Meta SEAL group in any of the two obturation techniques. In that work, gutta-percha and zinc-oxide eugenol-based sealer were obturated using continuous wave compaction technique, and single cone obturation with resilon point was used for Meta SEAL. Despite minor methodological variations, the outcome was comparable to our investigation.²⁶ Furthermore, as with many other investigations, the fracture resistance of teeth was measured in our study using a universal testing machine. The load was applied vertically along the teeth's long axis, which completely transferred the load, reduced bending moments, and lesser stresses due to the maximum stresses being positioned considerably more cervically. Because the study design replicates the support that alveolar bone provides for teeth, it is thought to resemble the clinical situation.^{5, 19, 20}

Conclusion

Adhesive root canal sealers are gaining popularity due to the "monoblock" idea; nevertheless, additional study is needed to fully comprehend the characteristics of these methacrylate-based sealers, especially Meta SEAL, in order to maximize their application in the endodontics sector.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study is supported by research grant for the student of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This research protocol was approved by the committee and permission for the study was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU/2021/8578).

Informed Consent Statement: Yes

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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